

THE UNHEARD VOICES: THE DECLINE OF YOUTH POLITICAL PARTICIPATION IN THE PHILIPPINES

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ABSTRACT

Political participation is a fundamental human right guaranteed to all citizens by the constitution; the right to vote is related to democracy and citizen empowerment. This research uses a quantitative and descriptive approach to investigate the decline in Filipino youth political participation. A survey was used and answered by 279 respondents selected at random and identified as youth students at Arellano University College of Arts and Sciences. The survey questionnaire solicited respondents' demographic information, electoral participation in the last election, and reasons for not voting. The findings revealed that a substantial proportion of the research respondents were youth single adults. Political, socioeconomic, institutional, and media variables are the most important influences on respondents' decisions to vote for candidates. However, reasons for not voting include personal, political, candidate competencies, electoral process, and health concerns. The research suggests that political engagement in the subject matter

investigated was influenced by the overall decisions of the electorate's decision to vote or not is influenced by various variables. It is also recommended that policymakers develop a comprehensive strategy. There should be policies in place to encourage more people to participate in politics and promote democracy.

Keywords: *political participation, Filipino youth, democracy*

INTRODUCTION

The history of the Philippines is shaped by a wide range of political movements and individuals, its struggles for independence, and the challenges posed by contemporary governance. Its dynamic political climate is also attributed to its broad and rich history of political participation.

Jose Rizal, a nationalist and revolutionary, played an important role in the Philippines' struggle for independence from Spanish colonial power and is regarded as one of the most significant figures in the country's political history. Jose Rizal's ideas and deeds inspired generations of Filipinos to stand up for independence and self-determination, paving the way for the establishment of the Philippine Republic in 1898. Rizal's beliefs on social justice, democracy, and the value of education are still relevant to Filipinos today, demonstrating how his contributions have had a long-term impact on the country's political development.

Today, political engagement in the Philippines is limited due to various restraints. Despite recent advancements, the Philippines continues to struggle with political violence, inequality, and corruption, which undermines the government. As observed by Youniss et al. (2002), there is an overall pattern of disengagement and apathy among people around the world, and the Philippines is no exception, as shown in the voter turnout in the 2022 national election at 80.38%. According to the data provided by Statista (n.d), this indicates that nearly 20% of registered voters did not vote in the 2022 national election. This pattern is also reflected in the data on national elections from 2001 to 2016. Indeed, it can be clearly said that political participation has steadily declined over time.

Political participation, as defined by Longley (2021), refers to citizens' political activity and involvement. Every citizen is valuable in politics, and politicians and scholars have justified democracy's distinct character by highlighting the role and importance of ordinary citizens in political activities. Activities such as voting, demonstrating, contacting public officials, boycotting, attending party rallies, participating in guerrilla gardening, publishing blogs, volunteering, joining flash mobs, signing petitions, purchasing fair-trade products, and even committing suicide have all been added to the list of nearly infinite participatory activities that influence politics and citizens' daily lives. (VanDeth, 2016).

Civil society emerged as an alternative to extra-parliamentary practices during the authoritarian Marcos dictatorship. Former President Cory Aquino's administration paved

the way for civil society political participation, highlighting the distinction between state-society ties in Philippine democracy prior to and following the period of Martial Law. The 1986 revolution prompted political and economic elites to recognize popular political power, resulting in a less limited ballot box. The communist left's defection to community organizations led to increased civil society political participation (Hutchinson, 2007).

In the Philippines, political participation research has primarily and generally focused on citizens' experiences with political involvement through organized groups, electoral behavior, including voting, and women's political participation. Women's interests in politics can be explicitly characterized by their efforts to organize as a political force at the local level and to run for a position that will recognize their qualities as public figures (Cunan-an-Angsioco et al., 2000). Although the country boasts of a few established communities as well as civic and political groups, through which people notably participate, it is undisputed and unquestionable that a significant portion of its citizenry does not engage politically through such avenues, and that almost everyone will, at some point or another, as individual citizens of the community, they can participate and become politically involved.

However, while women's political participation remains on an average scale, political participation among youths is declining, which is deemed vital for a viable democratic society now and in the future. Youth contributions and participation in politics are critical for a society with informed citizens and strong public health. According to the Commission on Elections, there are 67 million voters in May 2022 elections, and 52% of all registered voters are between the ages of 18 and 40, categorized as youth or young adults (Inquirer, 2022). Most voters are expected to be youths, which indicates that the outcome of the elections could be significantly influenced by the voting results of this demographic. They are a numerical force to be reckoned with, yet the experiences and different interests of the youth lead to divergent sentiments during elections.

Furthermore, youths' passion for political involvement is usually undermined since they are barred from participating in electoral procedures and public affairs. When we talk about politics and youth in the Philippines, the first thing that comes to mind is the cliché that Filipino youths are uninterested, if not apathetic, in politics, which has remained unquestioned to this day. Some studies tend to confirm this viewpoint. According to a survey of Filipino youth, political participation is one of the least significant aspects of their lives, after having a decent marriage, family life, stable employment, and a solid education (Weiss, 2020).

This research aims to examine the decline of Filipino youth's participation in politics during elections and identify the variables that lead to their refrain from this participation. Additionally, it seeks solutions to the problem and encourages increasing public involvement in the political process. Identifying the reasons for this decline can help policymakers develop measures that persuade more people to participate in politics and show support for democratic processes.

Research Questions

This research investigates the decline in youth political participation in the Philippines. Specifically, it sought answers to the following:

1. What are the reasons why there is a decline in youth political participation in the Philippines?
2. How does political participation influence the decision-making of the Filipino youth?
3. How can the government encourage more Filipino youth to participate in elections?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

To analyze the provided topic, this research employed a quantitative-descriptive approach. Identifying respondents with a personal understanding of the Philippine electorate was the first stage in conducting this research. Secondly, respondents were randomly surveyed to address the problem stated. The third phase comprises reviewing survey results and other secondary sources to provide context and background information on the declining level of youth political participation in the electoral process. The data survey is analyzed using descriptive statistics.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents in the research are individuals who are eligible to vote in the Philippine elections; that is, they must be between the ages of 18 to 24, registered or unregistered voters in the Philippines, and informed about the electoral process. Finally, they have to agree to participate in the researchers' survey.

Sampling Technique

The researchers utilized a random sampling technique to determine the appropriate number of respondents for this research. Random sampling is a probability sampling strategy that involves selecting respondents at random from a subset of a population. In this sampling procedure, every member of the population has an equal probability of being chosen (Cresswell, 2005). There were 279 respondents, including 160 male and 119 female electorates. The respondents were registered and unregistered Philippine voters from Arellano University's College of Arts and Sciences. The survey research design is suitable for use because the research required information from students who agreed to be surveyed confidentially.

Scope and Limitation

The research examines the reasons for the decline in youth political participation in the Philippines. It identifies the factors that cause Filipino youth to refrain from participating in the electoral process. It also sought solutions to the problem and promote greater citizen participation in the political process, identifying the causes of this decline to assist policymakers in developing interventions that encourage more people to participate in politics and support democracy.

Furthermore, it is vital to recognize and evaluate the research's shortcomings. The scope of the research is confined to Arellano University undergraduate students, specifically from the College of Arts and Sciences. Hence, the findings cannot be extrapolated to all youths in the country. The research also fails to collect perspectives and opinions from other youths attending various colleges and universities throughout the country, who may have different experiences. Thus, it should be noted that the research's scope is limited since it does not include all possible elements that could impact the cause of the decline in youth political engagement in the country.

Data Gathering Method

The researchers sent a letter of permission to Arellano University-College of Arts and Sciences, stating their intent to conduct a survey. Upon obtaining approval, they began collecting data from the target respondents. The researchers provided a consent form to the respondents that explains the purpose of the survey and guarantees the anonymity of their participation.

Data Analysis

To complete this research, the data provided by the respondents were analyzed and evaluated to provide the hypothesis and responses to research questions. The survey data was electronically processed and summarized to offer descriptive results for analysis and interpretation based on the designated research variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents by gender, educational program, voter's status, and civil status

Variable	Indicator	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	160	57.35

	Female	119	42.65
Educational Programs	Bachelor of Arts in Political Science	173	62.01
	Bachelor of Arts in History	26	9.32
	Bachelor of Arts in English	25	8.96
	Bachelor of Arts in Psychology	55	19.71
Voter's Status	Registered	237	84.95
	Unregistered	42	15.05
Civil Status	Single	250	89.61
	Married	29	10.39

Table 1 indicates the gender of the respondents, which is 57.35% male and 42.65% female. By educational programs chosen, 62.01% come from Bachelor of Arts in Political Science, 9.32% from Bachelor of Arts in History, 8.96% from Bachelor of Arts in English, and 19.71% from Bachelor of Arts in Psychology. By voter status, 84.95% are registered voters, while 15.05% are unregistered. Finally, in terms of civil status, 89.61% are single and 10.39% are married.

It may be drawn that the majority of the youths surveyed are registered voters in Philippine electorates, with most of them pursuing political science degrees. According to the data, most students studying political science are more informed and knowledgeable about the process of political participation than other youths enrolled in other programs.

Table 2. Factors That Influence Filipino Youth's Voting Decisions

Factor	Mean	Description
Political	7.17	Highly Dominant
Socio-Economic Factor	6.04	Dominant
Institutional	3.13	Moderately Dominant
Media	3.10	Moderately Dominant
Total Mean	4.86	Highly Dominant

Table 2 The political factors had the highest weighted mean of 7.17, showing a significant influence on youth voter decision-making during elections. Most likely, the majority of respondents strongly believe that political factors influenced their voting selections. Typically, awareness of political participation drives and dominates subsequent political decisions, events, and electoral processes. Increasing awareness as a strategy to increase youth political involvement could enormously impact democracy.

The socioeconomic factor emerged second in influence with a weighted mean of 6.04, indicating that it is the dominant factor in youth voters' decision-making when choosing candidates during the election. It established a boundary between the students surveyed and those who participated. It could possibly be argued that socioeconomic factors influence youth voter decision-making.

The institutional factor came in next with a weighted mean of 3.13, indicating a moderately dominant factor influencing youth voters' decision-making when choosing candidates during the election. The media also has a moderate dominance on youth voters' decision-making having 3.10 mean. Media advocacy promotes active participation in the election (Rahman & Bunaiya, 2022). According to Reyes (2019), this institution has significant influence in shaping the political and electoral scene today. Some media outlets, such as TV and radio, may portray elections as crucial for bringing about change in the country. In this circumstance, electoral participation will definitely increase.

The total weighted mean of 4.86 indicates that all four identified factors have a dominant influence on youth voter turnout. The results show that respondents' answers and ratings were consistent with the total mean.

Figure 1. Reason for not Voting in the Past Election

Figure 1 illustrates the respondents' political participation during the last election. Out of the 279 respondents, 114 (40.86%) participated in the last election. In comparison, 165 (59.14%) respondents did not participate in the last election, indicating a higher proportion of youth voters who did not vote compared to those who voted. The respondents cited five major reasons for not voting, including political, personal, health concerns, electoral processes, and candidate competencies.

Table 3. Reason for the Decline of Youth Political Participation

Reason	Frequency	Percentage
Political	75	45.45
Candidate Competencies	53	32.12
Personal	12	7.27
Electoral Process	18	10.91
Health	7	4.24
Total	165	100

As indicated in Table 3, more than half of the respondents did not vote in the previous 2022 election national election, owing mostly to political considerations, which were deemed the most significant factor impeding their electoral participation. Some respondents stated political reasons for prioritizing their viewpoints in participating in the election. Respondents agreed that prevalent political phenomena such as electoral fraud and vote buying, and many more were frequently responsible for the tarnishing of election outcomes' legitimacy. They saw this political practice as just abusive and out of control. Indeed, various abnormalities undermined the uncomplicated electoral processes in the Philippines (Abocejo, 2015).

Other reasons given included candidates' competencies, which accounted for 32.12%. They stated that several candidates must be qualified and capable to be elected. Candidates for elected posts require training, leadership experience, and certain skills needed for public service. The personal reason ranked third at 7.27%. Three respondents stated that voting and fulfilling their civic responsibilities were less essential than participating in their normal activities. Some people would rather do housework than vote. Meanwhile, electoral process came in fourth at 10.91%, with respondents citing poor electoral procedures during the election period. The least was 4.24% for health reasons, with some youth voters stating that they were not feeling well on election day and were unable to simply go to the voting station to participate in the democratic process.

Conclusions

The political participation is dependent on the truthfulness of the listed variables that determine how voters decide to engage in the political process. Indeed, political participation alters the landscape of democratic legitimacy; that is, when higher participation in elections is obtained, legitimate political objectives encourage voter participation. It is revealed that the respondents' participation in elections is heavily influenced by their overall decisions to vote or not vote in the election, which are shaped by compelling variables throughout the voting process. Individual voters' participation, whether voluntary or not, demonstrates a desire to decide and utilize their rights during an election.

Many voters did not vote due to political reasons, candidate competencies, and personal reasons. Filipino youth today value their perspectives in participating in the election and their desire for effective public leadership among elected officials. Meanwhile, personal concerns take place when an individual emphasizes personal interests over civic duty, business, work, family, and other responsibilities. The research found that reasonable and conscious voters prioritize their needs and wants. They choose candidates who are likely to meet those needs if elected to office.

Recommendations

The survey results show that policymakers should create a thorough and comprehensive approach. There should be measures in place to encourage more people to get involved in politics and support democracy. These are the recommendations based on the data gathered: 1) strengthening the awareness of the importance of political participation among youth; 2) reducing voter registration obstacles; 3) minimizing false and misleading information; 4) ensuring accessibility to polling precincts; 5) strengthening the campaign on the importance of political participation and democracy; 6) and finally, increased media influence in order to create a positive image and support for the government.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical guidelines were carried out throughout the study to maintain the integrity and quality of this research. Firstly, the researchers obtained permission from the Dean of the College of Arts and Sciences at Arellano University before they conducted the survey. Respondents were then oriented about the nature, purpose, and use of the collected data for the research. To safeguard their privacy, voluntary informed consent was secured from them through a signed agreement. They had the option to not participate in the survey if they did not want to.

Additionally, the respondents were guaranteed the confidentiality of the data shared and ensured that answered survey questionnaires would be handled and kept solely for academic purposes. Lastly, to generate impartial findings for this study,

objective and fair treatment of responses was highly observed throughout the data analysis process.

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